

Studies in Fluorenone. Part II.

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In the first paper in this series published under the caption "Attempts to prepare dyes from fluorenone" (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 637), a number of fluorenone-2-azomethine, fluorenone-azo, and fluorenonylamide derivatives were described.

The present paper deals mainly with the preparation of bisazo-compounds obtained by diazotising 2:7-diaminofluorenone and coupling the diazo-salt with various phenols and amines, *e. g.*, phenol, resorcinol, salicylic acid, β -naphthol, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, 1-naphthylamine-4-sulphonic acid, 1-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid, R-acid (2-naphthol-3:6-disulphonic acid), G-acid (2-naphthol-6:8-disulphonic acid), Cleve's acid (1-naphthylamine-6-sulphonic acid), Laurent's acid (1-naphthylamine-5-sulphonic acid), H-acid (1-hydroxy-8-aminonaphthalene-3:6-disulphonic acid), Schaffer's acid (2-naphthol-6-sulphonic acid), γ -acid (2-amino-8-naphthol-6-sulphonic acid), Chromotropic acid (1:8-dihydroxynaphthalene-3:6-disulphonic acid) and dimethylaniline.

Of the bisazo derivatives mentioned above, those with phenol, salicylic acid, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid and dimethylaniline form well defined crystals. The rest were obtained as amorphous or microcrystalline powder. The bisazo dyes are substantive to cotton but a few of them are not absorbed by cotton satisfactorily and even when absorbed the shades are not full. They also dye wool evenly from one per cent. sulphuric acid bath but shades on wool are invariably somewhat lighter than their shades on cotton.

Chanussot (*Anal. Assoc. Quim. Argentina*, 1927, 15, 5) obtained 2-iodofluorenone (m. p. 143-44°) by the oxidation of 2-iodofluorene.

2-Iodofluorenone has now been prepared from 2-aminofluorenone via diazo-reaction.

All attempts to obtain 2:2'-difluorenyl by the action of copper powder (Natur Kupfer C) on 2-iodofluorenone in nitrobenzene or in a sealed tube at temperatures varying from 150° to 350° were unsuccessful. Similar failure to obtain 2:2'-difluorenyl from 2-iodofluorene has been recorded by Korczynski, Karlowaska and Kierzek (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1927, 41, 65).

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Iodo fluorenone.—2-Aminofluorenone was diazotised (Diels, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 1764) and to this cold diazo solution an excess of potassium iodide solution gradually added with continuous stirring. The mixture was then allowed to remain at the ordinary temperature for about 1 hour and then cautiously warmed until there was no more evolution of nitrogen. The excess of iodine was now removed by sodium thiosulphate and the mixture allowed to stand overnight in a freezing mixture. Next day the separated solid was filtered and repeatedly washed with water. The residue was purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol. This operation was repeated thrice when finally the iodo compound was obtained as yellow needles, m. p. 144°. (Found: I, 41.8. $C_{13}H_7OI$ requires I, 41.5 per cent.).

Preparation of the fluorenone-2:7-bisazo derivatives.—2:7-Diaminofluorenone (Schmidt, Retzlaff and Haid, *Annalen*, 1912, **390**, 210) was converted into the hydrochloride by warming with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The clear solution was diluted and cooled to about 0°. The amine was tetrazotised in the usual way with the calculated quantity of sodium nitrite. After the diazotisation was complete the solution was quite clear and gave a slight reaction with iodised starch paper. The phenolic or basic constituents were then coupled with the tetrazo-salt in the usual way as with the tetrazo-salt of benzidine. The completion of coupling required from 24 to 41 hours, during which time the mixture was stirred at intervals. The dye stuff was then precipitated by the addition of acid or alkali, washed and purified. None of them melts below 290°. They give characteristic colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid, from which water precipitates them unchanged.

The bisazo derivatives obtained are described in the following tables.

Fluorenone-2:7-bisazo Derivatives.

(F = Fluorenone; D = Tetraazo-salt from 2:7-diaminofluorenone).

Name.	Method of preparation.	Appearance and solubilities.	Colour with conc. H ₂ SO ₄ .	Shades of dyeing		Analysis (N).	
				on cotton.	on wool.	Found.	Calc.
F-2:7-bisazo-bis-phenol	D + phenol	Deep brown needles from hot alcohol; moderately soluble in hot alcohol or water, sparingly soluble in hot benzene or acetone.	Deep reddish-violet	Orange yellow	Brownish-yellow	13.66	13.83 p.c.
F-2:7-bisazo-bis-resorcinol	D + resorcinol	Dark brown microcrystalline powder from alcohol; moderately soluble in hot water or alcohol, sparingly soluble in benzene.	Deep violet	Reddish brown	Light reddish brown	12.63	12.83
F-2:7-bisazo-bis-salicylic acid	D + salicylic acid	Deep brown needles from acetic acid; moderately soluble in hot acetic acid, sparingly soluble in alcohol, benzene or water.	Deep reddish violet	Orange yellow	Light brownish-yellow	11.16	11.02
F-2:7-bisazo-bis-β-naphthol	D + β-naphthol	Deep brown crystalline powder; moderately soluble in hot benzene, sparingly soluble in hot alcohol and insoluble in water.	Deep violet	Light shades of violet (practically unabsorbed)	Light violet	10.93	10.76

Fluorenone-2,7-bisazo Derivatives.

Name.	Method of preparation.	Appearance and solubilities.	Colour with conc. H_2SO_4 .	Shades of dyeing		Analysis (N).	
				on cotton.	on wool.	Found.	Calc.
F-2,7-bisazo-bis-2-naphthoxy-3-naphthoic acid	D + 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid	Brownish violet rectangular crystals from alcohol; moderately soluble in hot alcohol, acetic acid or water.	Bluish violet	Practically unabsorbed	Violet-brown	9.40	9.20 p.c.
F-2,7-bisazo-bis-1-naphthylamine-4-sulphonic acid	D + 1-naphthylamine-4-sulphonic acid	Red powder from hot alcohol; moderately soluble in hot alcohol, acetone or water.	Blue	No absorption	Light violet-red	12.53	12.39
F-2,7-bisazo-bis-1-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid	D + 1-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid	Deep reddish brown powder from hot alcohol; moderately soluble in hot water, benzene or alcohol.	Deep blue	Light shades of violet (full shades not obtained)	Violet-brown	8.47	8.23
F-2,7-bisazo-bis-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonic acid	D + R-acid	Reddish violet microcrystalline powder from acetic acid; moderately soluble in hot water or acetic acid and sparingly soluble in alcohol.	Bluish violet	Light shades of violet (full shades not obtained)	Violet-brown	7.04	6.82

Fluorenone-2:7-bisazo Derivatives.

Name.	Method of preparation.	Appearance and solubilities.	Colour with conc. H ₂ SO ₄ .	Shades of dyeing		Analysis (N).	
				on cotton.	on wool.	Found.	Calc.
F-2:7-bisazo-bis-2-naphthol-6:8-disulphonic acid	D + G-acid	Brownish violet powder from acetic acid; moderately soluble in water or acetic acid and sparingly soluble in alcohol.	Deep red	Light reddish-brown (full shades not obtained)	Reddish-orange	7.07	6.82
F-2:7-bisazo-bis-1-naphthylamine-6-sulphonic acid	D + Cleve's acid	Deep brown powder from acetic acid; moderately soluble in acetic acid, sparingly soluble in alcohol or water.	Blue	Very light brown (full shades not obtained)	Brown	12.88	12.79
F-2:7-bisazo-bis-1-naphthylamine-6-sulphonic acid	D + Laurent's acid	Deep brown powder from hot alcohol; moderately soluble in hot alcohol or acetone and sparingly soluble in hot water.	Blue	Violet-brown	Reddish-brown	12.87	12.79
F-2:7-bisazo-bis-1-hydroxy-8-aminonaphthalene-3:6-disulphonic acid	D + H-acid	Deep brown amorphous powder; moderately soluble in hot water, sparingly soluble in hot benzene or acetone.	Deep blue	Deep blue	Grey	9.21	9.65

Fluorenone-2:7-bisazo Derivatives.

Name.	Method of preparation.	Appearance and solubilities.	Shades of dyeing		Analysis (N).		
			Colour with conc. H ₂ SO ₄ .	on cotton.	on wool.	Found.	Calc.
E-2:7-bisazo-bis-2-naphthol-6-sulphonic acid	D + Schaffer's acid	Violet powder from hot alcohol; moderately soluble in hot water, alcohol or benzene and sparingly soluble in acetone.	Violet-blue	Violet-brown	Reddish-brown	8.41	8.23
E-2:7-bisazo-bis-2-amino-5-naphthol-6-sulphonic acid	D + γ -acid	Deep brown powder from acetic acid; moderately soluble in water or acetic acid and sparingly soluble in alcohol or acetone.	Blue-black	Bluish violet	Violet-brown	12.08	11.83
E-2:7-bisazo-bis-1:8-dihydroxy-naphthalene-3:6-disulphonic acid	D + Chromotropic acid	Bluish violet amorphous powder; moderately soluble in hot water, acetone or acetic acid and sparingly soluble in alcohol.	Deep greenish blue	Deep blue	Bluish-violet	6.60	6.42
E-2:7-bisazo-bis-dimethyl-aniline.	D + dimethyl-aniline	Deep brown needles from acetic acid; moderately soluble in hot alcohol, acetic acid or dilute hydrochloric acid and sparingly soluble in acetone or water.	Deep brown	No absorption	Brown	18.09	17.72

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